

IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LESSON USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE TEACHING OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

Khurshida Bakhtiyorovna Murodova

Teacher of the Department of Russian
Language and Literature of Karshi State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7556382>

Abstract: The use of modern interactive teaching methods is a prerequisite for improving the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language in accordance with modern educational standards. The article is devoted to the problem of using interactive teaching methods at the lessons of Russian language and literature. The study substantiates the didactic potential of this pedagogical technology, identifies the target system and the advantages of its use in the lessons of the Russian language and literature in modern school. In the work among the range of interactive technologies through theoretical analysis and selection the most effective methods that can be used in the framework of modern lessons of the Russian language and literature are indicated.

Keywords: interactive teaching methods, interactive learning, Russian language and literature lessons, the level of cognitive activity, gaming technology.

Arousing interest in your subject, maintaining student motivation, making the lesson interesting and effective in terms of mastering the material covered is not an easy task. However, there are many different pedagogical approaches to address this issue. Consider one of these methods - interactive learning. The principle of interactive learning is that the learning process takes place in conditions of constant, active interaction. Teacher and students interact; students cooperate, teaching each other. The lesson sets clear, defined goals, and all work is based on feedback. At the same time, the motivation to learn the language increases, the student's personality, creative abilities, his ability to think and speak Russian develop. The main forms of interactive learning include role-playing communicative games, speech situations, discussion games, interactive team games, case method, "POPS formula", project method, brainstorming, distance travel, competitions, performances, fairy tales, presentations, debates, discussions, mind maps, watching videos and listening to audio materials, etc. For students who speak Russian at an advanced level, interactive team games such as "Brain Ring", "What? Where? When?", "Connoisseurs Club". Such interactive games allow students to expand their knowledge about the country whose language they are studying, as well as to test the general level of knowledge, erudition, and logic. The situation of the competition is able to stimulate the mental activity of foreign students, forcing them to express their thoughts faster in Russian. Such role-playing games can be carried out when studying any topic, to control the assimilation of lexical and grammatical material. Among other things, role-playing games help to quickly adapt to the Russianspeaking environment, understand the realities of life in Russia, prepare for situations of everyday communication, and remove the language barrier.

The methodical technique "Opposites" is also aimed at expanding the vocabulary. You can use this technique both with minimal "starting" material and with extended vocabulary. The trick

is to pick up the opposite word, that is, the antonym. On the "starting" material, the following opposites are possible: yes -no, here -there, hello -goodbye, good -bad, fast -slow, difficult -easy, far -close, possible -impossible, etc. When studying extended vocabulary antonymic pairs are used: open -close, turn on -turn off, receive -send, always -never, war -peace, north -south, east-west, etc. "Guess the word" is an interactive technique that is used mainly at a basic level of Russian language proficiency. It consists in the fact that the student thinks of a word and explains it to the rest of the participants without naming it. The teacher can distribute the words to the students himself, focusing on any topic. For example, the word "winter": this is the time when it gets very cold in Russia it snows and people wear warm clothes. It is not so cold in my country at this time. We do not get that much snow. What is this? Watching and discussing videos, listening to audio materials. Videos of various content can be used at any stage of the lesson in accordance with its theme and purpose, and not just as additional material. Before showing the film, it is necessary to pose several (3-5) key questions to the trainees. This will be the basis for the following discussion. You can stop the film at pre-selected frames and have a discussion. Listening to audio materials, such as recorded news programs, TV debates, discussions, etc., helps students develop the necessary skills to understand rapid and spontaneous speech. An important aspect of interactive forms of learning is the work of students in small groups and in pairs. The teacher creates all sorts of situations where students can use their existing knowledge of the language in real communication. This type of work allows students to overcome the language barrier, learn to find errors in their speech and in the speech of their interlocutor, independently correct each other. Discussing various topics and questions in groups and pairs, students have the opportunity to work out the maximum number of options for speech constructions for the most complete and understandable expression of thought. Another interactive form of learning is the creation of speech situations. For example: you are in an unfamiliar city and do not know how to get to a hotel whose address you forgot; you have a toothache, you need to make an appointment with the dentist; you have a high temperature, you need to call a doctor at home; you have a sore throat, you went to the pharmacy for medicine, etc. The main task of such exercises is to activate your speaking skills in Russian. The research process used the methods of objectivity, logic, analysis and synthesis of scientific knowledge. In the course of this research, the importance of Bloom's taxonomy was objectively revealed. Interactive learning issues are devoted to the work of many scientists and specialists: S. Yu. Kurganova, V. Khane, M. V. Karman, and others. To exercise training using interactive methods, the teacher must have pedagogical skills. It should be brought to a high degree of educational and educational skill, reflecting a special collapse of methods and receptions. Interactive learning is a special form of organization of cognitive activity. It has in mind quite concrete and predicted goals. One of these goals is to create comfortable learning conditions, such under which the learner feels their success, its intellectual consistency, which makes the learning process itself. This method in modern school is perceived as a method for collective production of new ideas. The "brainstorming" method makes it possible to develop logical thinking, it is argued to express its point of view, activating speech skills. Algorithm for using the method "Brainstorming": 1 step - formulate a problem associated with theme lesson. Pupils formulated the problem: "Why is the work called" pomegranate bracelet "? - Pupils of Shaoid B. answered this question like this: " This subject became the center of all the work. " And Bakhtier K. thought and answered: "Grenade

is a symbol of passion, love, because the name about strong and clean love." 2 step - divide students into several groups, taking into account their interests: I divided class students to 4 working groups. 3 step - Remove the tension to create a favorable atmosphere: We listened to the musical excerpt, which became a soundtrack for the film on this work. The guys themselves picked up fragments from the film and musical passages. 4 Step - "Brain Attack": assault, set: I suggested the students to come up with an end to the story. The guys offered two options: the heroine understands which high and pure love "hurt her with his wing," but nothing wanted to change in his life; Others - the hero and heroine are combined into a family. 5 step - fix ideas on paper. Pupils write their ideas on the papers. 6 Step - Select and evaluate the best ideas. Pupils and I took the best ideas. 7 step - to organize an expert group of 3 students who choose the best ideas. From each group, we chose one student, which should choose the best ideas. 8 step - report results. Pupils report results. 9 Step - Public Protection. Each group argues their answers. 10 step - decision making. We enrolled the scores of each group and summed up. We productively use this method in literature lessons when studying the lyrical works of Russian poets. In the context of the educational process for schoolchildren, it is important not to just learn to mechanically memorize and reproduce the proposed material, but to master the skill of establishing causal relationships.

References:

- 1.Chjen Elena V. «Personally-oriented approach in upbringing students in the system of lifelong education» ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. ISSN: 2249- 7137 Impact Factor SJIF 2020= 7. 13 ,17-21 бет
- 2.Файзуллаева Х. Э. «Работа по фразеологии при изучении имени числительного»Science and education. Scientific journal. ISSN 2181-0842. Volume 1, ISSUE 2, May 2020, 574-577
- 3.Fayzullayeva KH.E. "Metaphor explanation methods when studying artistic" Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal. Research for revolution. ISSN № - 2581-4230. Impact Factor-5.785. Volume 6, ISSUE 7, July-2020, 298-301p
- 4.Lebedinsky S.I., Kamilova N.N. Methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language: textbook. Allowance. – Minsk, 2020.
- 5.Turaeva S. N. Actual problems of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language: Materials of the II Intern. Scientific-practical. conf. – Ufa, 2020.